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A basic strategy for growth factor inhibition in cancer.

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The strategy dictates targeting the 1) growth factor/GF receptor, the 2) associated up-regulated/compensatory kinase, and the 3) TSC family member that responds to loss of that GF stimulus by induction of a gene from the TSC family.